

Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities

WP3- ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development

Deliverable D3.5: "ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-final version"

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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**ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and
Development-final version**

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market Trend Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.5 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-final version” is used to document the ToyLabs MVP as well as the final versions of the software components designed and developed in the framework of WP3.

The definition of the ToyLabs MVP refers to the identification of the actors involved in ToyLabs and of the final list of User Stories per Actor, identifying the expected and implemented functionalities of the ToyLabs platform.

The four components which form the main elements of the platform are: the ToyLabs Core Platform (TCP), the Market and Trend Analysis (MTA) component, the Partner Matching and Negotiation (PMN) component and the Augmented Reality Feedback (ARF) component. In the present deliverable these components, which have been designed, developed and delivered in the framework of WP3, are described in terms of architecture, usage flows and requirements definition.

The type of the deliverable 3.5 is “Other” in terms that the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the components which have been designed and developed during WP3 following a continues process: Developing an initial version of each component and - through close collaboration with the end/pilot users validating the different functionalities - proceeding to updates and improvements in an iterative way until all the user requirements fully covered.

All the outputs of WP3 which are described in the present final deliverable are publicly accessible and can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D3.5 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-final version” is used to document the ToyLabs MVP as well as the final versions of the software components designed and developed in the framework of WP3.

The definition of the ToyLabs MVP refers to the identification of the actors involved in ToyLabs and of the final list of User Stories per Actor, identifying the expected and implemented functionalities of the ToyLabs platform.

The four components which form the main elements of the platform are: the ToyLabs Core Platform (TCP), the Market and Trend Analysis (MTA) component, the Partner Matching and Negotiation (PMN) component and the Augmented Reality Feedback (ARF) component. In the present deliverable these components, which have been designed, developed and delivered in the framework of WP3, are described in terms of architecture, usage flows and requirements definition.

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1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of D3.5 is the following:

- Section 2 presents the final version of the ToyLabs MVP: the actors involved, the epics and the final set of user stories per actor
- Sections 3 provides the definition and description of the ToyLabs Core Platform which serves as a baseline for designing and developing the three ToyLabs added-value components in the framework of WP3
- Sections 4, 5 and 6 include the detailed descriptions of the added-value components, providing respective flow diagrams and definition of the final log of requirements for each component
- Section 7 concludes the deliverable at hand and the work performed in WP3.

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As the final deliverable of the Work Package, the present deliverable summarises all the work performed in the framework of the WP3 tasks and previously has been presented in D3.1 – D3.4.

On the basis of the input received during the piloting (taking place in WP5), the final versions of components have been documented and developed.

All the components designed, developed and presented in the deliverable consist input to WP4 tasks, where their integration takes place towards the establishment and validation of the final version of the ToyLabs Integrated Platform.

2 TOYLABS PLATFORM DESIGN

2.1 The ToyLabs MVP

MVP stands for “Minimum Viable Product” as is the output that is able to minimize the risk of failure and improve the value generated. An MVP is the version of a product which has the highest return on investment versus risk. The MVP pinpoints the minimum set of features that are necessary for a product to be deployed and validated, and this defined the characteristics of the initial version of the ToyLabs components developed and delivered. Starting from the ToyLabs MVP the development team was able to deeply learn about the end users needs and what were their expectations. This first version of all the components has been, throughout the project, gradually improved, populated with extra features and finally released in an integrated ToyLabs Platform open to everyone.

The ToyLabs MVP has been defined early in the project on the basis of a set of user stories and following a perspective identifying which user stories are the most important for each type of actor/ user of the ToyLabs software components. As described above, the ToyLabs MVP has been developed on the basis of an initial user stories backlog and provided to the consortium in order to get feedback on the different components delivered. Since this first release and during the continues development and validation of the software components by the end users, some user stories have been omitted, some have been amended and, of course, new user stories have been created, as the more the end users were testing and using the developed software, the more precise they could become in identifying their exact needs and their vision about the optimal design of the ToyLabs solution.

Proceeding to such changes and improvements, several versions and subversions of the ToyLabs components have been internally released to the consortium, ending at the final version which also incorporated all comments received during the piloting phase. The complete set of user stories which accurately defines the final fully functional and validated version of all the ToyLabs software components, is presented in this section.

2.2 Actors & Epics

The identification of the “actors” that utilise the ToyLabs platform has been since the beginning a crucial challenge. Actors are seen from the perspective of the system in this case, thus a real user (e.g. an individual) may have different roles on the system, resulting in the definition of more than one system actors (for example the same individual can be an “unregistered user” and then become a “registered” user, and be also at the same time an “Organisation Member” if he is given such rights).

However, at this point one does not distinguish internal actors in components to be integrated, but is only concerned about the main “system actors” of the platform as a whole.

The final actors identified for ToyLabs components is the following:

Table 1: TOYLABS Actors

Actor	Description
Visitor	A user that lands on the ToyLabs platform page and browses the platform without logging in
Ordinary User	A user that is registered in the platform and can access content and features that are not available to visitors
Manufacturer	A user that takes up the role of a manufacturer, who is responsible for creating a product and steering the whole process of the toy creation
FabLab	A user that is representing a FabLab, who can collaborate with Manufacturers
Expert	A user that has a professional capacity as an expert, who can collaborate with Manufacturers and FabLabs. Under this category, both Safety Experts and Childhood Experts are included. Those are different groups, having different business scopes. However, since their envisaged operation in the platform is similar, they are grouped under 1 actor altogether. Emerging user stories during WP3, might lead to the separation of those two sub-types and their eventual distinction as 2 different actors
Product Owner	A user that has initiated the process of creating a product, being either a manufacturer himself, or choosing a manufacturer to delegate design and production to the latter
Organisation Owner	A user that has set up an organisation structure in the platform and is able to manage it
Organisation Member	A user that has join an organisation structure

Following the identification of actors, “Epics” were created, which are large concepts that describe (at high-level) operations that a user wishes to do, and those are broken down then in more specific parts, the “User stories”. In the case of ToyLabs, Epics are describing the major operations of the different components (and of the platform) and were since the beginning utilised to group together user stories in the direction of better structuring the overall development backlog. As parts of larger “Epics”, “User stories” can be considered as smaller idea segments, utilised to provide high-level definitions of requirements, describing a feature told from the end user’s perspective.

2.3 Toylabs User Stories sheets

In the paragraphs to follow, the final list of user stories defining the Toylabs platform components as developed and delivered are being presented. The user stories are divided by actor in order to be clearer which user type has each requirement.

As far as it concerns the representation of the different user stories, a user stories sheet is provided for each actor, including the following fields:

- ID: an arbitrary ID composed by the actor's name (2letter) and a number;
- Epic: representing a "group" of user stories, trying to provide a broader context regarding a specific goal of an actor.
- User Story: A textual description, truncated in the following pieces:
 - o *As an <actor role>*: indicating the role of the subject of the story (e.g. the actor identified above) (selection from actor's list)
 - o *I want <action (to do a thing)>*: the functionality to be added to the solution (free text). This is the core concept of a requirement.
 - o *so that <reason>*: the added value of the development suggested (free text)

2.3.1 User Stories for Actor "Visitor"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
VI.1	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to find out more about a toy which appears publicly in the platform		I can see details, pictures and description of the toy
VI.2	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to go through a short tutorial page on how the ToyLabs platform operates		I understand the value and operation principles of the platform
VI.3	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to view all public products of ToyLabs in the main platform		I can understand which products are supported by the platform
VI.4	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to see a sort description of each product, including the product owners' details, comments and likes		I can find out more about a product and the organisation behind it
VI.5	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to find details about the consortium partners		I can make contact with them
VI.6	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the terms of use of the platform and related information		I can choose whether I want to carry on the registration procedure or not
VI.7	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to see the list of registered organisations in the platform		I can find possible collaborating organisations
VI.8	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to display a public AR model of a product with the help of the ToyLabs AR Engine		I can have a virtual representation of the product in a real setting environment
VI.9	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to provide feedback to AR models in case this is allowed		I can provide my comments without being logged in
VI.10	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to register/log in with minimal details		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
VI.11	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to use my social network credentials to register/log in		I can be part of the ToyLabs platform
VI.12	Registration/Log In		Visitor		to be able to request a reset of my password		I can set a new one in case I forgot it

2.3.1 User Stories for Actor “Ordinary User”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OU.1	Registration		Ordinary User		to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process		I can have a more complete personal profile
OU.2	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to choose the role that I will have in Toylabs (Manufacturer, FabLab, Safety Expert, Childhood Expert, Ordinary User)		I can enjoy the services offered to the role I belong to
OU.3	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to edit my personal profile information		I can have a more complete personal profile
OU.4	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to permanently remove my account credentials from the system		I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users
OU.5	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to specify a new Organisation that I belong to in case this does not exist		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.6	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the basic information of the entity		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all
OU.7	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to my Organisation to provide the extended capability information of the entity		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
OU.8	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		during the registration process to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation
OU.9	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		register my Organisation if not already done during registration		I can add my organisation to the platform and become the Owner of it
OU.10	Organisation Selection		Ordinary User		to be able to join an existing organisation, pending the approval of its Owner		I can collaborate with my co-workers of the same organisation

OU.11	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User	to view public designs on the website based on their creation date	I can see the most recent ones
OU.12	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User	to sort public designs on the website based on their popularity	I can see the ones with the most comments
OU.13	ToyLabs Products Browsing		Ordinary User	to be able to share information about a product on my social media accounts	so that I further disseminate information about a product
OU.14	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to be able to send a direct message to the Organisation behind a product	I establish a communication channel with an Organisation
OU.15	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to be able to view messages sent to me and reply	I can continue communication with an Organisation/ other users
OU.16	Communication Actions		Ordinary User	to get notified when I have a direct message received	I know a response to my request was provided
OU.17	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to comment on a product and take part in an ongoing discussion	to make my opinion heard
OU.18	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to comment on a public AR model in the ToyLabs platform	I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
OU.19	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to vote specific features on a public AR model, on my mobile device	I can instantly provide feedback
OU.20	Feedback Provision		Ordinary User	to upload a screenshot of the public AR model	I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model
OU.21	Product Initiation		Ordinary User	to be able to initiate a product creation phase	I can become a product owner

2.3.2 User Stories for Actor “Manufacturer”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
MA.1	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer		to be able to view invitations from product owners for new product's creations		get notified on whether I have been selected as a manufacturer

MA.2	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer	to be able to reply positive and sign a NDA or negative to product creation invitation		I can notify the product owner of my decision
MA.3	Manufacturer Contract Opportunity		Manufacturer	to retrieve, sign and send back a contract sent to me by a product owner		I can then start the production process
MA.4	Product Handling		Manufacturer	to be able to see a list of all products I am handling		I can select details on specific ones
MA.5	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to able to initiate the partner matching module and search for partners		I can select other collaborators to work with
MA.6	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to see a list of collaborators suggested by partners I already work with		I can build a more trusted cycle of collaboration
MA.7	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to invite a partner to a step of the toy creation process (Design/Prototype/Mass Creation)		I can explore collaboration opportunities
MA.8	Partner Matching		Manufacturer	to include an NDA to the invitation from the Partner Matching module to a specific toy creation process		I can protect my IPRs in that process
MA.9	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	see all partners that have signed an NDA to a product		I know with who I am sharing information
MA.10	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	to send a contract to a collaborator already added to a toy creation process step (have signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
MA.11	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	accept (double sign) a signed contract from a collaborator		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
MA.12	Contract Negotiation		Manufacturer	see all partners that have signed a collaboration contract to a product		I know with whom I have an open contract in a product
MA.13	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to be able to initiate the Market Trends and Social Feedback module		I can understand the sentiment of users on a product or a manufacturer and trends discussed in web2.0 channels
MA.14	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to be able to choose between Trends Analysis and Social Feedback Analysis		I can learn about current trends in the toy industry or receive feedback about specific brands and products respectively

MA.15	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to select the social media channels to be used by the sentiment or the trend analysis module		I can understand the opinion or the desire of the crowd in the web
MA.16	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	To create market sets (brand/ product combinations) in my organisation's profile		I can load them in any new analysis without performing extra work
MA.17	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to select specific words in the sentiment or trends analysis module		these are used for mining the web
MA.18	Market Trend Analysis Setup		Manufacturer	to enable the "influencers' mode" of the sentiment analysis module		I can find people with influencing power in a broad web audience on a specific topic
MA.19	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to see the positive, negative and other online comments on my product or my brand from the sentiment analysis module		I can define a strategy for improvement
MA.20	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to see visualised analytics based on the results of the sentiment or the trend analysis module and receive comments on the visualisations		I can better understand the results of the module the opinions of my collaborators
MA.21	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to see related concepts about search terms		Related concepts to search terms may can drive to results about trends and feedback from users
MA.22	Market Analytics Visualisation		Manufacturer	to download and save the visualisation graphs as CSV, XLSX, JSON files		I can further analyse the results offline
MA.23	Design handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Master" Design		I can have multiple versions of the same master design
MA.24	Design handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Design" version		I can open up the design phase of the process
MA.25	Design handling		Manufacturer	to be able to turn the visibility of a "Design" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information		it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page
MA.26	Design handling		Manufacturer	to populate the "Design" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)		I can share this information with my future collaborators
MA.27	Design handling		Manufacturer	to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Design" version		I can fine tune my idea

MA.29	Design handling		Manufacturer	to archive a "Design" version		I can move on to another phase or publish an updated design
MA.30	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to open a new "Design" version once the previous one is closed		I work with my collaborators on the improved design that resulted from the previous thread
MA.31	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to create a new "Prototype"		I can open up the prototyping phase of the process
MA.32	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to be able to turn the visibility of a "Prototype" version to public, that will showcase only basic design information		it can be displayed publicly in the ToyLabs showcase page
MA.33	Prototype handling		Manufacturer	to populate the "prototype" version with material relevant to this phase (files, specification, cost analyses, etc.)		I can share this information with my future collaborators
MA.34	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to attach an AR model to a prototype		I can share it with collaborators
MA.35	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to accompany the AR model with a simple questionnaire for AR user		they can instantly provide comment from the AR devices
MA.36	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to view the feedback of my collaborators on a "Prototype" version		I can better understand the feedback from the prototype
MA.37	Prototype AR Enrichment		Manufacturer	to view feedback captured from the AR model		I can better understand the feedback from the prototype

2.3.3 User Stories for Actor “FabLab”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
FA.1	Fablab Contract Opportunity		FabLab		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him
FA.2	Contract Negotiation		FabLab		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator

FA.3	Contract Negotiation		FabLab	to sign a contract, sent to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
FA.4	Feedback to Designs		FabLab	to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.5	Feedback to Designs		FabLab	to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.6	Feedback to Designs		FabLab	to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.7	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.8	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.9	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.10	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to be able to play with controls embed in the AR model		I can have a better experience with the conceptual model
FA.11	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
FA.12	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
FA.13	Feedback to Prototypes		FabLab	to upload a screenshot of the AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model

2.3.4 User Stories for Actor "Expert"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
FA.1	Expert Contract Opportunity		Expert		to get notified about a direct invite I might get from a manufacturer		I can reply to him

FA.2	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to be in a position to accept/reject a direct invitation by signing the NDA		I can become a collaborator
FA.3	Contract Negotiation		Expert		to sign a contract, send to me by a manufacturer		I can ensure that there is a relationship of trust
FA.4	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.5	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Design" version I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.6	Feedback to Designs		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a design version		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.7	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to be able to download all material in a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can better understand the design
FA.8	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment (and attach files) on the overall issues of a "Prototype" I have been invited to		I can provide my input in terms of updated material back to the thread
FA.9	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to directly and privately contact a manufacturer about a prototype		I can establish a private communication channel
FA.10	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to comment on an AR model in the ToyLabs platform		I can provide Feedback back to the manufacturer
FA.11	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to vote specific features on an AR model, on my mobile device		I can instantly provide feedback
FA.12	Feedback to Prototypes		Expert		to upload a screenshot of the AR model		I can show to the manufacturer my display of the model

2.3.5 User Stories for Actor “Product Owner”

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
PO.1	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to be able to fill in the basic information about a new product		I can provide more details on that product
PO.2	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		engage in discussions with users of the platform based on my product		I can get online, direct feedback

PO.3	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to mark a product as released and update its description		users can find more information about it in the public website
PO.4	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to specify crucial information about my product (like cost, technical requirements, material requirements, etc.) about my product		I can have a thorough description of my product's specifications
PO.5	Product Information Filling		Product Owner		to archive a finished product		it is not displayed on my dashboard
PO.6	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to search for a Manufacturer in the platform using the partner matching module		to assign him the responsibility to create my product
PO.7	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to be able to accompany the invitation to a manufacturer with an NDA		I can protect the IPRs of my idea
PO.8	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		to send a contract to a manufacturer (who has signed the NDA)		I can formally engage with him
PO.9	Manufacturing Initiation		Product Owner		accept (double sign) a signed contract from the manufacturer		I have a trusted and formal relationship with him
PO.10	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to monitor the overall creation process of a product		I can understand to which state it is
PO.11	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to view all information on the product, as selected by the manufacturer		I can have a more detailed view on the different actions and decisions
PO.12	Product Monitoring		Product Owner		to be able to see a list of all my products		I can select details on specific ones

2.3.6 User Stories for Actor "Organisation Owner"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OO.1	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the basic information about my Organisation		an informative profile of my Organisation becomes available to all

OO.2	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to edit the extended capability information of my Organisation		a detailed profile of my Organisation's capabilities becomes available to all
OO.3	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		so that I further disseminate information about my Organisation
OO.4	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to have my organisation's profile "public" by default		it is listed in the public organisations list of the platform
OO.5	Organisation Information Filling		Organisation Owner		to configure my Market Analysis settings for my organisation		I can load them in a new analysis instead of creating them from the start
OO.6	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to get notifications about people asking to join/leave/accept or reject Ownership transfer of my Organisation		I can have an idea on who is a member of my organisation
OO.7	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to accept or reject invitations of other people wanting to join my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OO.8	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to delete my organisation		it is no longer part of the ToyLabs platform
OO.9	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to invite other team members to join ToyLabs and my Organisation		I can have all my team online to collaborate
OO.10	Organisation Management		Organisation Owner		to be able to remove users from my Organisation		I can manage the access of users to my Organisation's information

2.3.7 User Stories for Actor "Organisation Member"

#	EPIC	USER STORY					
		As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
OM.1	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to ask to get removed		I no longer see the data referring to the organisation
OM.2	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to accept the transfer of the ownership of an Organisation to my Name		I can become the Owner of it

OM.3	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to share information about my Organisation through my social media accounts		I further disseminate information about my Organisation
OM.4	Participating in an Organisation		Organisation Member		to be able to represent my organisation in any product under development		I can provide feedback, comments and data for the products under development, representing my organisation

3 TOYLABS CORE PLATFORM

3.1 Introduction

The ToyLabs Core Platform (TCP) This is the main infrastructure that powers the ToyLabs platform and acts as the host environment for all other components that need to be integrated.

In more detail, the TCP is responsible for handling the following main operations requested from the overall project platform:

- Platform Browsing
- Registration/Log In
- Profile Editing
- Organisation Selection
- ToyLabs Products Browsing
- Communication Actions
- Feedback Provision
- Product Initiation
- Prototype Request
- Product Handling
- Design Handling
- Prototype Handling
- AR model Handling
- Feedback management
- Product Information Filling
- Manufacturing Initiation
- Product Monitoring
- Organisation Creation and Management
- Participating in an Organisation

3.2 Core Platform's Flow Diagram

The user is able to browse all the "public" pages of the ToyLabs platform, as no authorization is required to see the information that is publically published. Upon landing to the user login/registration page, he is able to either log in using his credentials (in case he has been already registered in ToyLabs), or to initiate the registration process. This process asks the user for specific information, and once he is accepted as a registered user he may choose whether to join an existing

organization or create a new one. As a next step, the user is able to browse the platform's private spaces, and also to edit his profile.

Figure 1: User Onboarding Workflow

The creation of a product on the ToyLabs platform is initiated by a user by specifying some basic information about the product. Afterwards the user is able to create different design or prototype version, and in each one add collaborators and work with them in order to improve the product. It needs to be noted, that during the whole process, specific parts (like "Add Collaborator") are supported by other components such as the PMN component.

Figure 2: Product Management Workflow

3.3 Core Platform Functional Requirements

The complete list of functional requirements of the core platform is presented in the following table. A Requirement ID, a Short-Name and a detailed Description is provided for each requirement. The final delivered version of the software fully covers all the defined requirements.

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION
TCP.01	Products showcase	The system to display all public products
TCP.02	NDA and ToR	The system to display the platform's NDA and Terms & Conditions documents
TCP.03	List of Registered Organisations	The system to display a list of registered organisations in the platform
TCP.04	Product Details	The Visitor to see more details about a product
TCP.05	AR Download	The Visitor to be able to download an AR model posted to a product through the mobile app
TCP.06	Simple Signup	The Visitor to be able to register with his email
TCP.07	Social Signup	The Visitor to be able to register with his social media accounts
TCP.07.01	Login	The Visitor to be able to login with his email
TCP.07.02	Social Login	The Visitor to be able to login with his social media accounts
TCP.07.03	Password Reminder	The Visitor to be able to request his password to be reset
TCP.08	Profile Filling	The Ordinary User to be able to fill in his profile information
TCP.09	Profile Editing	The Ordinary User to be able to edit his profile information
TCP.10	Profile Visibility	The Ordinary User to have a private personal private

TCP.10.1	Organisation Creation	The Ordinary User to create a new Organisation
TCP.11	Organisation Profile	The Organisation Owner to fill in the information about his organisation
TCP.11.1	Organisation Profile Editing	The Organisation Owner to edit the stored information about his organisation
TCP.13	Organisation Profile Visibility	The Organisations' profiles to be open/ available to all platform users
TCP.14	Joining Organisations	The Ordinary User to ask to join an existing Organisation
TCP.14.1	Organisation Join Request Notification	The system to notify the Organisation Owner for a join request
TCP.14.2	Organisation Join Request View	The Organisation Owner to view the join request
TCP.15	Organisation Join Request Response	The Organisation Owner to accept/reject the join Request
TCP.16	Organisation Member Leaving	The Organisation Member to leave an organisation he has joined
TCP.17	Notifications	The Ordinary User to see notifications of any kind
TCP.18	Sending Direct Message to User	The Ordinary User to send direct messages to other users in the platform
TCP.18.1	Sending Direct Message to User	The Ordinary User to send direct messages to other users in the platform
TCP.18.2	Routing of Message to Organisation Owner	The System to send any message referring to an Organisation to the Organisation owner
TCP.19	Inbox view	The Ordinary User to view incoming direct messages
TCP.20	Direct Message Reply	The Ordinary User to respond to direct messages he receives
TCP.21	Product Details	The Ordinary User to see more details about a product if it is public
TCP.22	User Comments on Product	The Ordinary User to comment on a product

TCP.23	User Comments on Design	The Ordinary User to comment on a design
TCP.24	User Comments on Prototype	The Ordinary User to comment on a prototype
TCP.25	Product KickOff by User	The Ordinary User to initiate the creation of a product
TCP.26	Product KickOff by Manufacturer	The Manufacturer to initiate the creation of a product
TCP.27	PMN Component	The Manufacturer to launch the PMN component
TCP.28	MTA Component	The Manufacturer to launch the MTA component
TCP.28.01	ARF Component	The Manufacturer to launch the ARF component
TCP.29	Master Design	The Manufacturer to create "Master" Design
TCP.30	Design Versions	The Manufacturer to create a new Design version
TCP.31	Close a Design Version	The Manufacturer to be able to archive a Design version
TCP.32	Design Visibility	The Manufacturer to turn a Design public or private
TCP.33	Design Information	The Manufacturer to fill in information to accompany the Design
TCP.34	Design Edit	The Manufacturer to edit information of a Design
TCP.35	Prototype Creation	The Manufacturer to create a Prototype
TCP.36	Prototype Deletion	The Manufacturer to archive a Prototype
TCP.37	Prototype Visibility	The Manufacturer to turn a Prototype public or private
TCP.38	Prototype Information	The Manufacturer to fill in information to accompany the Prototype
TCP.39	Prototype Edit	The Manufacturer to edit information of a Prototype
TCP.40	Prototype to AR Link	The system to link the ARF component to a prototype
TCP.41	FabLab Comments on Product	The FabLab to provide comments on a Product
TCP.42	FabLab Comments on Design	The FabLab to upload documents to a Design

TCP.43	FabLab Comments on Prototype	The FabLab to provide comments on a Prototype
TCP.44	Expert Comments on Product	The Expert to provide comments on a Design
TCP.45	Expert Comments on Design	The Expert to upload documents to a Design including comments or new versions
TCP.46	Expert Comments on Prototype	The Expert to provide comments on a Prototype
TCP.47	Product Information Filling	The Product Owner to fill in information about a product
TCP.48	Product Monitoring	The Product Owner to view the progress of a Product
TCP.48.1	Own Product Listing	The Product Owner to see a list of his Products

4 MARKET AND TREND ANALYSIS COMPONENT

4.1 Description

This component is intended to give the user an easy-to-use tool that will provide him with the appropriate information - through various, intuitive charts- to help him on the one hand identify market trends for his domain of interest (Trends Analysis) and on the other hand gain a deeper understanding of customers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction on specific topics (either products/toys or brands) and as a result on their brand perception, campaign efficiency and competitors' position in the market (Social Feedback Analysis).

Through this component, the toy manufacturer, or any intended user, will be able to:

- Explore visual analytics and gain insights on how trends are being generated in web and social media;
- Interact with the analytics and draw useful conclusions on emerging market trends for the toy industry that may serve, combined with the manufacturer's experience, as recommendations and initial, raw ideas about future toy designs;
- Download the charts and graphs of the visual analytics as CSV, XLSX or JSON files for further analysis
- Acquire social feedback on specified by the manufacturer's terms of interest;
- Gain deeper and quantitative insights on crowd's perception about a brand or brand's product;
- Explore visual graphs about a manufacturer's market position (as reflected by both the number and semantics of mentions in web) as well as their competitors' so that he can gain actionable insights for improving his competitive position.

4.2 Architecture

The Market and Trend Analysis component consists of three main, distinct parts; the User Interface, the Communication Layer and the Natural Language Processing and Analytics engine. Figure 3-1 depicts the component's high level architecture, namely these three layers along with their internal structure. It should be mentioned that the component's architecture did not undergo any major updates since D3.2 of the present Work Package because the technologies, libraries and programming languages required for developing the component and connecting it to the ToyLabs platform are pretty standard.

The User Interface is responsible for providing the user with insights into the collected data, while guiding him to apply filters, make intuitive queries and browse the results through advanced visualisations. The component's User Interface in question is integrated in the core platform's User Interface. The basic technologies used for this layer are PHP and JavaScript.

The Communication layer manages and directs the flow of data between the two other layers, namely the component's User Interface and the Analytics engine. The Python Django REST framework will be used for this purpose, in conjunction with a TCP module that will handle the authorisation and the communication between the UI and the Python portion of the analytics engine.

Finally, the Natural language processing and analytics engine is responsible for the data retrieval, data processing and the implementation of all required computations to perform emotion analysis and identify trending topics. As a result, this layer is used to extract data from source and process them in a way that can feed the web interface. The basic technologies that are used are the "Elasticsearch" engine, the "Couchbase server" database, the "NLTK" framework and the "Scikit learn" library.

The Market and Trend Analysis component gets integrated in the ToyLabs Core Platform by expanding the platform's user interface and connecting the engine to the backend. As seen in Figure 3-1, the integration takes place in the platform's middle application logic layer through a list of API calls that will request specific information from the module. The module's frontend is being integrated, as already stated, using JavaScript and the libraries D3 and AMCHARTS. It is based on the built-in modules of VueJS to communicate with a RESTful API. The module stores its data in a separate database than that of the core platform. Finally, the user initialises the module in the product development's Research phase, which is the second phase after concept definition, and prompts the user to start either a Market Trends or a Social Feedback analysis.

Figure 3: Architecture of Market and Trend Analysis Component

4.3 Flow Diagrams

In this section, all updates in the component's flow diagrams, with respect to the ones presented in the context of D3.3, are presented. In this context, some steps were omitted while others created. The final workflows however, represent very well the final solution of the component.

In this context, the first workflow presented in Figure 3-2 has to do with the configuration of each newly created project. The user must initialise a harvester in order to start a trend or a social feedback analysis and this is achieved via a group of user settings on the platform. These settings are related to the data sources that are to be used for the analysis, the keywords, hashtags or phrases considered to be relevant to the analysis that will follow, and which must be included in the harvesting data and data's language.

The select language choice was removed because it was realised the toy domain is not represented very well in social media, in languages other than English. Consequently, the results we would get would be dubious to say the least and would not represent the majority of the population. Moreover, the user will no longer receive a notification e-mail when his analysis is complete because the procedure was optimised and as a result the visualisation can be viewed immediately after completing the settings.

Figure 4: Project Configuration Workflow

Apart from the general configuration of the component, the user will be able to choose between a Market Trend and a Social Feedback analysis.

Starting with the Trend Analysis workflow, according to the flow diagram that is presented in Figure 3-3, the user may either load past saved search settings or configure the search settings for his analysis, starting from the harvester (i.e. project configuration) ones. In that view, he may restrict search parameters on specific keywords, sources, languages or influencers' accounts for the analysis that will follow. He may afterwards provide to the platform additional settings regarding the time period for the analysis, being able to go back in time and compare analysis reports. Finally, before starting the analysis, the user is requested to provide specific meaningful concepts of interest (i.e. baby dolls) and parameters (e.g. colour, material) that will be presented and formulate the visualisations accordingly in order to provide to the user useful and meaningful information customized to his needs and industry's "language". After that, he can initiate a trend analysis and apply specific filters to charts in order to acquire the needed information. The user can also save these preferences for future use.

Figure 5: Trend Analysis Workflow

Finally, Figure 3-4 represents the flow diagram for the user that wants to implement Social Feedback analysis. For the social feedback analysis, the user is firstly asked to either load a past saved search for social feedback or to configure the search settings for his analysis, starting from the harvester settings. This, as well as the two consecutive steps, come in direct alignment with the Trend Analysis Workflow, since here also the user is requested to optionally configure further certain search parameters and specify the time period of the analysis.

After that, the user is asked either to create a new market set for the social feedback analysis or to choose one from his saved market sets. The “market set” as introduced and defined in the context of ToyLabs is a representation of the market for the manufacturer in question as he perceives it. Therefore, the manufacturer is asked to provide how the component will search for his brand (i.e. keywords), his products, as well as for his competitors and competitors’ products. Each market set may be a subset of the market as the manufacturer wants to represent it for his analysis. To make it clearer, not necessarily all his competitors or all his products are listed in each market set, but only the ones that he wants to compare for the specific analysis needs.

Then the user can start social feedback analysis and apply, as was the case in trend analysis, specific filters to charts in order to take the information he needs and to save these preferences for future use.

Figure 6: Social Feedback Workflow

4.4 Functional Requirements

In this sub-chapter the functional requirements of the Market trends & Social Feedback component will be listed. Given that this is the last update of Work Package 3, the following requirements largely represent the final version of the tool as can be seen in the ToyLabs platform and the functionality it offers to the platform’s users. Specifically:

1. **Component Initialization:** The user shall be able to initiate the component when the concept phase of a product development process is complete, by entering the research phase. The user shall then be able to select between creating a Social Feedback Analysis or a Market Trend Analysis. The platform shall allow the user to initiate a Social Feedback Analysis only if his organization’s Market Analysis settings have been configured.
2. **Component Parameter Settings:** The user shall be able to specify the name of the analysis. The user shall be able to enter keywords to be used as search terms and view examples through help texts that may help him correctly fill in the appropriate keywords. The user shall be able to select the

data sources to be used for the analysis and whether he wants influencer mode to be active or not. In the case of a Social Feedback analysis, the user shall not have the option to activate/deactivate influencer mode. However, in both types of analyses, the user shall be able to provide the time period for data retrieval for the analysis. The user shall be able to edit these settings at any point of the analysis.

- a. **Market Trends Concept Settings:** The user shall be able to provide specific meaningful concepts of interest and parameters that shall be presented and formulate the visualisations accordingly. The user shall be able to add, update and remove the concepts and parameters.
 - b. **Social Feedback Organisation Settings:** An organisation operating in the ToyLabs platform, shall be able to configure its market analysis settings beforehand in the organisation's profile. The organisation shall be able to also set brand, product combinations for the retriever to search. Members of the organisation shall then be able to load these settings when initiating a new analysis. The organisation shall be able at any point to add, update and remove keywords, brands and products from its configuration.
3. **Component Visualisations:** When the settings of the analysis are set, the user shall be able to see visualized analytics by clicking on the view analysis button. Although there are some common graphs and charts, depending on the type of analysis the user shall see different visualisations. In the case of a Market Trends analysis the user shall see analytics based not only on the keywords but also on the concepts and parameters set. In a Social Feedback analysis the user shall be able to see the overall sentiment for the brands and products that he selected and related topics per brand and product. The user shall be able to download and save the graphs as CSV, XLSX or JSON files for further analysis. Platform users that have the right to view the analysis shall be able to leave comments to provide their feedback.

5 PARTNER MATCHING AND NEGOTIATION COMPONENT

5.1 Description

The Partner Matching & Negotiation (PMN) component is a tool that can be used by users to inquire about collaborators, inside the Toylabs Platform, allowing them to set up formal partnerships, that will lead to collaborative design and development of products.

In more detail, the PMN component is responsible for handling a handful of operations that range from partner searching to matchmaking between different platform users, enabling specific collaboration opportunities.

5.2 Architecture

The PMN component is an infrastructure that relies on a three-tier architecture.

The backend consists of a MySQL database which is being used to store data regarding the different partners, as well as other information, such as active or past collaborations. The middle layer is responsible for the application logic and executes the partner search queries as well as the different partner matching algorithms.

A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the following figure.

Figure 7: PMN High Level Architecture

More specifically, the updated PMN High Level Architecture consists of:

The **User Interface**, which in turn consists of:

- The **Searching Interface**, which gives us the opportunity to search for a partner, by name or by matching criteria
- The **Negotiations/Messaging Interface**, which makes the exchange of messages, between the interested parties, feasible, in order to, start a collaboration, exchange contracts, or other legal documents
- The **Evaluation Interface**, setting the platform for the partners to evaluate and provide feedback on their collaboration, when a project is closed or archived.

The **PMN component logic**, composed of:

- The **Partner Matching Query Engine**, which is responsible for collecting data from the Search Interface and to provide ratings for the Partner Info, Capabilities and Feedback Repository.
- The **Partner Engagement Engine**, in order for a collaboration to initiate, but also for monitoring the collaboration status
- The **Partner Evaluation Engine**, liable to collect feedback on every partner, aggregating the provided feedback on their collaborations, so that their ratings can be summed up.

The **Toylabs Platform Database**, formed by:

- The **Partner Info, Capabilities and Feedback Repository**, in order to collect data on each partner, in any collaboration, providing data to this effect
- The **Collaboration Status Repository**, which stores the collaboration status (pending, active, negotiating, etc.)
 - The **Negotiations Repository**, where the discussions on a collaboration agreement are stored, as well as, contract and non-disclosure agreement documents.

5.3 Flow Diagrams

The PMN component's main objective is to allow users to seek for collaborators. This is based on the process of triggering a query which returns the possible collaborators that match the user's search criteria, which can be constantly refined until a short list is displayed. Out of the short list, the user may choose a preferred potential collaborator and send an NDA accompanied by a collaboration request. A negotiation among the two parties takes place with the support of the component, including exchange of documents and draft agreements. A successful negotiation leads to exchanging and storing the contract which defines the agreement terms and can be used by involved parties as reference document.

The following diagram represents the workflow defining the operation of the component:

Figure 8: PMN Workflow

5.4 Functional Requirements

The complete list of functional requirements of the component is presented in the following table. A Requirement ID, a Short-Name and a detailed Description is provided for each requirement. The final delivered version of the software fully covers all the defined requirements.

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION
PMN.01	Partner Search	The Seeking User to initiate a search session
PMN.01.01	Partner Type Specification	The Seeking User to specify the type of partner he is looking for
PMN.01.02	Search Criteria	The Seeking User to select from a list of partner type-specific filter
PMN.01.03	Query Editing	The Seeking User to edit his query by changing his options
PMN.01.04	Query Results	The system to present the partner matching results to the Seeking user
PMN.01.05	Partner Information Browsing	The Seeking User to view details for each result row retrieved
PMN.02	Partner Selection	The Seeking User to select a collaborator out of the list for sending an invitation
PMN.03	Invitation Notification	The system to send a notification to a selected collaborator about an invitation
PMN.04	Invitation Notification Browsing	The matched partner to view a notification
PMN.05	View NDA	The matched partner to view the NDA attached to the invitation
PMN.06	Respond to Invitation	The matched partner to respond to a notification positive or negative
PMN.07	Notification of invitation acceptance	The system to notify the Seeking User regarding the acceptance/rejection of his invitation from a Matched Partner
PMN.07.01	Attaching collaboration contract	The Seeking User to attached a collaboration contract document to be sent to a match partner for a design or a prototype
PMN.08	Signed Collaboration Contract Return	The Matched Partner to send back the signed collaboration contract document to the Seeking User

PMN.08.01	Storing of Active Contract	The Seeking User to sign the collaboration contract document and upload it in the platform
PMN.09	Active Contract Notification	The system to notify the Matched Partner that a collaboration contract document has been signed by both parties
PMN.10	View active contracts	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contact
PMN.11	View active contracts for a design	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contract to a product design
PMN.12	View active contracts for a prototype	The Seeking User to view the Matched Partners that have signed a contract to a product prototype

6 AUGMENTED REALITY FEEDBACK COMPONENT

6.1 Description

The Augmented Reality Feedback Component (ARF) is a tool used by end user that allow responsive and interactive presentation of 3D models with advanced capabilities.

Main goal of this tool is to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs.

The ARF component will uses 3 different modules: Questionnaire Creation to obtain feedback from user, Augmented Reality System for model presentation (rotation, modifying parameters like color, textures, etc) and Voting System used to know specific features on an AR model on mobile devices.

6.2 Architecture

The ARF component is an infrastructure that relies also on a three-tier architecture.

The backend consists of an MySQL¹ database with several tables which is being used to store server path for previously uploaded 3D models, textures or other parameters on one side on other side a table should be defined with standard tracking parameters ready to be used by end user or product owner (jpg, pdf, ...)

On the User side the ARF component is supported by a survey infrastructure that can help products owners and end users to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs. This survey infrastructure will be integrated on general survey engine module.

Also on user side, the ARF component will use a Voting System, this infrastructure will be integrated using general voting engine module developed on platform.

¹ <https://www.mysql.com>

Figure 9: ARF High Level Architecture

The Toylabs iOS Application is built on latest iOS SDK (11.2) using Swift version 4. The minimum iOS version supported is iOS 11.0. In order to retrieve and send the required data, the app sends HTTP Requests to a RESTful API. The supported formats for ar-models are the following: *.fbx*, *.obj*, *.3ds*, *.stl*, *.dae*, *.scn*.

For the presentation of AR-models, the app uses Apple's AR Kit.

6.3 Flow Diagrams

The ARF component is used to allow users (Childhood Experts/End-Users, FabLabs , etc.) to send feedback to the owners/ developers of a product on predefined 3D Models and product definition.

The figure below presents the workflow performed by a product that is willing to showcase an AR model. He is able to check for existing material on the platform, develop new material and after defining the target audience launch the AR model and explore the results of the feedback.

Figure 10: ARF Manufacturer Workflow

On the other side, the following figure shows how experts, FabLabs and other individuals or organizations are able to select an AR model (probably on their mobile phone), explore it through its visualization features and then provide feedback to the manufacturer, that could be either in the form of a structured questionnaire, or through a voting system.

Figure 11: ARF End user Workflow

6.4 Functional Requirements

The complete list of functional requirements of the component is presented in the following table. A Requirement ID, a Short-Name and a detailed Description is provided for each requirement. The final delivered version of the software fully covers all the defined requirements.

ID	NAME	DESCRIPTION
ARF.01	AR uploading	The system to be able to receive an AR model by a user
ARF.01.01	AR Uploading Log	The system to record the owner and the date of upload of an AR model
ARF.01.02	AR Entry editing	The AR model owner to edit the AR model's metadata and accompanying information
ARF.03	AR Entry Updating	The AR model owner to update an existing AR model
ARF.04	AR Entry Deleting	The AR model owner to delete an already uploaded (by him) AR model
ARF.05	AR Comments Linking	The system to open a commenting session for the AR model
ARF.06	AR Questionnaires Provision	The system to provide sets of questions with a 5-star rating system to the AR model owner
ARF.07	AR Questionnaire Save	The AR model owner to save a questionnaire
ARF.07.01	AR Questionnaire Update	The AR model owner to update a questionnaire
ARF.07.02	AR model URL creation	The system to create a download link for each AR model
ARF.08	AR Model Access	All collaborators on a design or prototype of a product to get access to the AR model
ARF.09	AR Model Publishing	The AR model owner to publish openly/set as public his AR model
ARF.10	AR Model Visualisation	The end-user to initiate the visualisation of an AR model
ARF.11	AR Model Commenting	The end-user to comment on an AR model
ARF.12	AR Model Questionnaire Responding	The end-user to answer on a questionnaire of an AR model
ARF.13	AR Model Screenshot Feedback	The end-user to upload a screenshot of an AR model
ARF.14	AR Model User Social Sharing	The end-user to share the AR model in his social network

ARF.15	AR Comments Viewing	The AR model owner to access the comments on an AR model
ARF.16	AR Questionnaire Results	The AR model owner to access the results of a questionnaire

7 CONCLUSIONS

The present deliverable includes the design documents of the Toylabs software components, referring to the last/ final released version of all the components after the completion of the software validation which took place during the piloting phase of the project.

For each component, the complete list of requirements which has been produced through an evolutionary process throughout the project with the active participation of the end users has been presented.

Of course, even if in the framework of the present deliverable the components are being described and examined separately, they have actually all been included in the final integrated version of the Toylabs Platform which has been validated by the pilot users as a whole. The inclusion of the components in the integrated platform has been completed following the integration process defined and following in Work Package 4 (see D4.1-D4.4).

At the end of the project, all the Toylabs software components are in mature state, fully operational and thoroughly tested. Of course, in the post-exploitation phase, which is the period after the end of the project that the technical partners plan to continue supporting and assist in the evolution of the platform, further improvements maybe introduced, always on the basis of needs expressed by the Toylabs users, referring not only to the consortium partners but to all the active members/ users of the Toylabs platform.